

THE CONTRIBUTION OF BANKING SECTOR TO THE GROWTH OF THE NIGERIAN ECONOMY

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Abstract

As a result of the fact that numerous economic actors in the productive sector are winding up due to their inability to obtain loans from the financial institutions or the cost of borrowing is excessive, this study examined the contributions of the banking sector to the growth of the Nigerian economy from 1986 to 2020. The study specifically examined the effects of bank' credit, banks' deposit and banks' assets on economic growth in Nigeria which was measured using real GDP. The data were sourced from the CBN statistical bulletin and analyzed using the Ordinary Least Square Regression and the Granger causality test. The findings of the study revealed that bank deposits and bank credit have negative and significant effects on economic growth. On the other hand, banking assets has positive and significant effects on economic growth in Nigeria. The researcher therefore recommended among other things that; banks should restructure the conditions of the credits extended to the private sector in such a way that would ensure that such loans are beneficial for productivity and not counterproductive and that banks also restructure the model of handling deposits to ensure that they are channeled to the most beneficial and productive investment outlets

KEYWORDS: bank credits, bank deposits, bank assets, economic growth, financial institutions

Introduction

The economic progress of a state is hinged on the robustness of the financial segment in general. The banking system, world over is the nucleus of the economy that provides the hub where funds and others economic activities interrelate. The banking sector plays dynamic role in the development and growth of the Nigerian economy by mobilizing savings and channeling them for investment purposes (Petkovski, and Kjosevski, 2014). The growth of this segment decides how it will be able to successfully and effectually carry out its major role in the mobilizing of capital from excess to deficit sector of the economy. Though formerly, the key function of banks was financing organized trade, commerce and industry, but now they provide finance to agriculture, small-case business and small borrowers (Singh, 2011). The sector has also helped in facilitating the business transactions of individuals and organizations and helped improve economic development.

Despite the challenges it faced, the Nigerian banking sector could be said to have performed relatively well in the post consolidation era (Mohammed, 2017; Ishioro, 2017). A very important part of a country's financial system is the banking sector and it constitutes a key provider of finance to business. Banks play a crucial role in the progress and expansion process of a nation. Traditionally, the duty of banks in an economy is to enable a well-organized payments system and to serve as a channel for the application of monetary policies. A bank's prime purpose is financial intermediation, accepting deposits, making loans at variety of maturities either fixed or variable rates and making of money through interest rates spread by charging for services provided (Yakubu, Abokor, and Balay, 2020; Bakare, Isaac and Samuel, 2015). The development of a financial system is critical in spurring growth of the economy while a financial system without prospects of development retard's economic growth of a country. A functional banking system facilitates the exchange of goods and services, provides facilities and encourages individuals to save and efficiently channels the funds to productive investments.

Ghimire and Giorgioni (2013) in their study found a positive impact of banks financing long-term growth in the economy. However, the trend in the banking sector leads to the increase in economic growth rates in any economy. This argument has been confirmed worldwide by many empirical researches. Therefore, economic growth theory believes that financial institutions especially banks are considered a useful instrument for improving the productive capacity of the economy and it is an important internal source of funds for any country especially in the early stages of economic growth. Undoubtedly, a vibrant and robust financial system has been

identified as a vital catalyst propelling the growth rate of an economy (Prochniak and Wasiak, 2017; Puryan, 2017).

The trajectory of the development of the Nigerian banking sector has over the years been characterized by numerous fluctuations and instabilities which can be traced to 1892 when the business of banking really commenced in Nigeria (Akpansung and Babalola, 2011). The Nigerian banking sector has not been able to measure up to its expectations as the driver of economic growth and development in Nigeria in spite of the banking reforms implemented so far. The poor performance of the banking sector has been attributed to numerous problems that are being faced by the sector such as inadequate capital, high nonperforming assets which had led to frequent distress in the banking sector and collapse of some banks in the past (Sanusi, 2012). The link between the financial sector and the growth of the economy has been weak. The real sector of the economy, most especially the high priority sectors in Nigeria which are also said to be economic growth drivers are not effectively and efficiently serviced by the financial sector.

The objective of this study is to determine the impact of bank deposit on economic growth in Nigeria, examine the influence of the bank credit on the Nigerian economic growth and examine the effect of banks' total assets on economic growth in Nigeria.

Conceptual Review

Bank and Banking system - According to Barone (2019) a bank is a financial institution licensed to receive deposits and make loans as well as other services like wealth management, currency exchange and safe deposits. A bank can also be defined as a financial institution that is licensed to accept deposits from the public and create credits through lending activities. Deposit money banks are institutions that collect deposits, grant credits, and render other financial services for profit purposes (Akinwale and Obagunwa, 2019). Akujuobi and Nwezeaku (2015) asserted that deposit money banks perform the role of accepting deposits, lending and safe keeping of valuables, as well as creating money through lending activities. The banking system is therefore a network of instruments, institutions, procedures and regulations that organizes the transfer for funds from savings to investments (Yakubu, Abokor and Balay, 2020).

Bank Credit -Bank credit involves an arrangement between a bank and customer in which financial resources are made available to the customer in terms of credit with a promise to repay the credit at a future period with interest. According to John and Terhemba (2016), bank credit is the process of making money available to a customer based on some agreed terms with regards

to repayment with interest. Bank credits are sourced from depositors' funds therefore; banks are debtors to the depositors of funds and creditors to the borrowers of funds (Ogunmuyiwa, Okunneye and Amaefule, 2017).

Access to bank credit strengthens productive assets by ensuring investment in productive sectors, education or health sector which have ripple effect on the growth of the economy (Akinwale and Obagunwa, 2019).

Bank Deposits -A deposit account is an account in which the bank agrees to take custody of the customers' money, thereby agreeing to be liable to pay either on demand or at an agreed date. These accounts could come with interests or bank charges depending on the agreement between the bank and the customer or the type of deposit account involved. Basically, there are three types of deposit account namely; Savings deposit account, Demand or current deposit account, and fixed time or termed deposit account.

Economic Growth -Economic growth is the increase in the capacity of an economy to produce goods and services, compared from one period to another. Economic growth can be measured in nominal terms which include inflation, or in real terms, which are adjusted for inflation. Many authors have defined the term 'Economic Growth' as follows:

Economic growth is the increase in the productive capacity of an economy. It is a sustained increase in the production of goods and services of a nation during a period of time (Olowofeso, Adeleke and Udoji, 2015). According to Bakare, Isaac, and Samuel (2015), economic growth is the positive change in the production level of goods and services and significant improvement of a country over a certain period of time. The term economic growth is described as the positive and continuous increase in aggregate goods and services produced in an economy within a given period of time. This means that the average worker in a given economy becomes, on average, more productive perhaps through use of more advanced technology or higher training or on the job skill improvement as well as specialization. It is also conceivable to realize aggregate economic growth without rise in average marginal output through increased labour force resulting from extra immigration, higher birth rate or reduced death rate. Also, the discovery of new or better economic resources brings about economic growth. An epitome of this is the discovery of gasoline; proceeding to the detection of energy-generating power of gasoline, the

economic worth of petroleum was comparatively low, but with the increased economic value of the product comes economic growth for the country in possession of the crude.

Theoretical Review

Endogenous Growth Theory - This Research work is anchored on the Endogenous Growth Theory. This theory proposes two competing predictions on how the finance sector contributes to economic growth - 'supply-leading' and 'demand-following' dichotomy. In the first set of models, output (Y) is expected to be a direct function of the capital stock (K) and capital productivity (A) as given by equation (1): $Y=AK_t$

The theory asserts that financial growth rate and the increase in capital can raise the proportion of savings funneled to growth or may increase the productive activities of capital leading to growth. Growth theory assumes that the interest rate plays the main role in equilibrating an economy's savings and investment. According to the neo-classical Golden Rule, the optimal growth path is equal to the real interest rate. The link between finance and economic growth may run through various transmission channels.

In this simple model, there are three probable transference mechanisms from financial intermediation to growth. Firstly, the role of financial intermediaries to assess and choose investment projects, if effectively performed, raises the returns on investment. The regular capital output of those assets, realized by real assessment and inspecting by intermediaries, will translate into economic growth. Secondly, the possibility of portfolio diversification by holding financial assets allows individual agents to undertake riskier and more specialized investment projects. The holding of foreign assets, for instance, decreases the exposure towards domestic economic shocks. The opportunity to share risks via the capital market might induce investors to invest a higher fraction in riskier projects, which on average tend to be more profitable for the economy. Thirdly, the availability of fund creates incentives to invest a larger share of savings in long-term projects, which are perceived as more profitable.

This theory explains how the possession and circulation of various financial assets by the commercial banks improve the overall productivity of investments thereby improving economic growth. The newer growth theory (endogenous theory) fits the real world perfectly well and has important policy implications (Contessi and Weinberger, 2009). This is because it tracks the progress of output per capita to two main bases: savings and efficiency. This implies that both factor accumulation and efforts to utilize it drives growth. The salient point of this theory is that

factors that bring about growth are within the economy and the improvement in productivity can be linked directly to extra investment in human capital.

The Table below is a summary of the Empirical Review

AUTHOR / YEAR	PERIOD	COUNTRY	TOPIC	VARIABLE	METHOD OF ESTIMATION	MAJOR FINDINGS
Yakubu , Abokor and Balay 2020	1970 - 2017	Turkey	The Impact of Financial Intermediation on economic growth in Turkey	Money Supply, Bank Deposit and Domestic Credit	Autoregressive Distributed Lag(ARDL), Bounds testing and Error Correction Model (ECM)	Financial intermediation significantly influences economic growth in both short and long run.
Akinwale and Obagunwa 2018	1981 - 2017	Nigeria	The Effect of Bank Credit on Economic Growth in Nigeria	Credit to Manufacturing Sector (CMS), Credit to Agricultural Sector(CAS), Real GDP(RGDP) and Credit to General Commerce(CGC)	Augmented Dickey – Fuller(ADF), Johansen C – Integration, Error Correction Model and Pairwise Granger Causality technique	The Johansen Co – Integration test reviewed that there is a long run relationship among the variables
Agbo and Nwankwo 2018	1981 - 2013	Nigeria	The Effect of Financial Sector Development on the Economic Growth of Nigeria.	Money Supply, Minimum Rediscount Rate, Exchange Rate, Banking Sector Credit, Credit to Private Sector, Market Capitalization and Foreign Direct Investment	Dickey Fuller Unit Root and Ordinary Least Square Technique	The multiple regression result shows that money supply, minimum rediscount rate and exchange rate have positive and insignificant effect on economic growth
Mohammed 2017	2000 - 2015		The Impact of Some Banking Sector Indicators(Credit Facilities, Depositors Fund, the Number of Branches and Interest Rate) on Gross Domestic Product	Credit Facilities, Depositors Fund, the Number of Branches and Interest Rate	Ordinary Least square regression model	Banking credit are positively related to economic growth however interest rate, customers deposit and number of branches did not significantly impact economic growth.

Odufuye 2017	1992 - 2015	Nigeria	Impact of Bank Credit on The Nigerian Economy Growth	Gross Domestic Product, Commercial Bank Credit to Small and Medium Scale Enterprises, Credit to Private Sector, Money Supply and Interest Rate as for Bank Credit	Ordinary Least Square(OLS)	Commercial bank credit to small and medium scale enterprises, credit to private sector, money supply and interest rate had an insignificant impact on gross domestic product.
Petkovski and Kjosevski 2014	2014	Central and South Eastern Europe	Does Central and South eastern Europe Economic Growth get Influenced by Developing Banking Sectors	Banking Credits, Interest Rate, Ratio of Quasi Money and Gross Domestic Product	Generalized method of moment (GMM) dynamic panel method	They found that banking credits and interest margin are negatively related to economic growth
Ishioro 2017	1970 – 2013	Nigeria	Banking Sector Reforms and Economic Growth	Economic Growth and Bank Sector Reform	Autoregressive Distributed Lags(ARDL) and Bounds Test	Banking sector credit to the private sector was negative and statistically insignificant in economic growth in Nigeria
Adekola 2016	2005 – 2014	Nigeria	Effect of Banks Profitability on Economic Growth in Nigeria	Return on Asset and Return on Equity of the Banks and GDP	Ordinary Least Square Regression	Increasing Proportion of banks profitability will significantly change the gross domestic product in Nigeria and the study concluded that the profitability of banks has a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Abugamea 2016	1995 – 2014	Palestine	The Relationship Between the Banking Sector Development and Economic Growth	Credit Lending, Lag credit, Economic Growth and Banking Efficiency	OLS Regression Estimation and Granger Causality test	OLS result showed a significant impact of bank size with a negative sign, insignificant impact of credit lending with a marginal one for lag credit and insignificant impact of efficiency on economic growth.
Okafor, Chijindu and Ugwugbe 2016	1981 – 2014	Nigeria	Causal Relationship Between Deposit Money Bank Credit and Econom Growth in Nigeria	Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), Private Sector Credit (PSC), and Broad Money SS (M2)	Vector Autoregressive Analysis (VAR) and Granger Causality Test.	There is a unidirectional Causality running from private sector credit and broad money supply to economic growth as measured by real GDP
Frikha and McMillian 2016	2005 – 2012	Egypt, Bahrain, Jordan, Kuwait, Pakistan, Saudi, Arabia, Qatar, Sudan, Turkey, and United Arab Emirates	The Roles of Islamic Banks in The Growth of Gross Domestic Product in 10 Developing Countries(Egypt, Bahrain, Jordan, Kuwait, Pakistan, Saudi, Arabia, Qatar, Sudan, Turkey, and United Arab Emirates)	Economic Growth	Ordinary Least Square Regression	They found out that conventional banks support economic growth
Ayunku and Etale 2014	1977 – 2010	Nigeria	The Relationship Between the Banking Sector Development and Economic Growth in Nigeria	Trade Opns(TO), Credit to Private Sector(PCR), Dom. Credit(DC), Dep. Liability(DL), Interest Rate(INT), RGDP	Augmente Dickey Fuller (ADF), Phillips Perron (PP) Unit Root Test, Johansen and ECM	The result of the study revealed that TO, DC and INT have positive relationship with RGDP while PCR and DL have a negative relationship with RGDP.
Abdusalaun and Ibrahim 2013	2013	Nigeria	Banking Sector Development and Economic Growth	Credit to Private Government and Interest Rate Spread	Auto-Regressive Distributed Lags	Credit to private govt. exp. and interest rate spread exert negative influence on growth in the long-run
Hamza and Khan 2014	2014	Pakistan	The Effect of Banking Sector Performance in Economic Growth	Bank Deposit, Investments, Advances, Profitability and Interest Earnings	Ordinary Least Square Regression model	This revealed that deposits, advances, profitability, interest earnings and investment have positive relationship with economic growth

Methodology & Model

This study adopted the ex post facto research design. The ex post facto research is a systematic empirical study in which the researcher does not in any way control or manipulates the independent variables because the situation for the study already exists or has taken place. This design was chosen specifically for its suitability to the type of data used in the study which is the time series data. The time series data are secondary data recorded periodically in a serial manner. This kind of data is free from manipulation as it is already established in secondary sources. The time series data used in this study were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin (2020) which was downloaded from the internet. The literatures highlighted and reviewed in this study were obtained from journals and financial agency reports.

This study uses a similar model to the study of Mohammed (2017) who expressed economic growth as a function of credit facilities, depositor's funds, interest rate and the number of bank branches. However, this study models economic growth (RGDP) as a function Of Bank Deposits (BDEP), Banks' Credit to Private Sector (BCPS) and Bank Total Assets (BTAS).

The functional model of the study is expressed thus;

$$RGDP = f(BDEP, BCPS, BTAS) \quad 3.1$$

The functional model is restated as an econometric equation which includes the regression coefficients and the error term

$$RGDP = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 BDEP_t + \alpha_2 BCPS_t + \alpha_3 BTAS_t + \mu_t \quad 3.2$$

Where;

α_0 = The intercept or constant term of the dependent variable

$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$ = regression coefficient

μ_t = the error term

Data Presentation and Analysis Descriptive Statistics

	BDEP	BCPS	BTAS	RGDP
Mean	6584.957	6757.711	11423.62	38574.98
Median	1337.296	1096.536	3047.856	31709.45
Maximum	31456.96	29051.61	43305.54	71387.83
Minimum	18.13760	15.24745	39.67880	15237.99
Std. Dev.	8608.971	9027.163	13994.89	20476.78
Skewness	1.175015	1.091202	0.943928	0.438826
Kurtosis	3.355056	2.784666	2.493951	1.576325
Jarque-Bera	8.237699	7.013504	5.570958	4.079137
Probability	0.016263	0.029994	0.061700	0.130085
Sum	230473.5	236519.9	399826.6	1350124.
Sum Sq. Dev.	2.52E+09	2.77E+09	6.66E+09	1.43E+10
Observations	35	35	35	35

Source: *E-views 11.0 Descriptive Statistics Output, 2022*

As shown above, bank deposits has amounted to an average of ₦6,584.95bn annually over the review period with its highest figure reaching ₦31,456.9bn and a lowest value of ₦18.14bn. Overall, the deposits accumulated by deposit money banks has amounted to ₦230,473.5bn. Likewise, banks' credit to private sector has amounted to an average of ₦6,757.7bn annually over the review period with its highest figure reaching ₦29,051bn and a lowest value of ₦15.25bn. Overall, the credit issued by deposit money banks to private sector has amounted to ₦236519.9bn. The banks have held asset positions at an average of ₦11,423.62bn annually with an all-time high figure of ₦43305.54bn. Economic output has amounted to ₦38,574.98 on the average each year.

Data Analysis

This section is split into two (2) subsections; the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression analysis and the Granger Causality Test. The Ordinary Least Square regression analysis reveals the direction of relationship or prediction between the dependent and independent variables

while the Granger causality test reveals the flow of causation or effect between the dependent and independent variable.

Ordinary Least Square Regression Analysis

Dependent Variable: RGDP

Method: Least Squares

Date: 01/18/22 Time: 12:40

Sample: 1986 2020

Included observations: 35

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
BDEP	-0.643601	0.812426	-0.792197	0.4343
BCPS	-2.777431	0.998806	-2.780751	0.0091
BTAS	3.579497	0.585573	6.112806	0.0000
C	20691.34	1184.911	17.46236	0.0000

R-squared	0.947560	Mean dependent var	38574.98
Adjusted R-squared	0.942486	S.D. dependent var	20476.78
S.E. of regression	4910.777	Akaike info criterion	19.94346
Sum squared resid	7.48E+08	Schwarz criterion	20.12122
Log likelihood	-345.0106	Hannan-Quinn criter.	20.00482
F-statistic	186.7185	Durbin-Watson stat	0.581343
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Source: *E-views 11.0 OLS Regression Results, 2022*

As shown above, Banks' deposit negatively ($B = -0.6436$) and insignificantly ($p = 0.4343$) predicts economic growth in Nigeria. This indicates that every billion naira increase in the value of bank deposit can be used to marginally predict a proportional decline in economic growth by 643 million naira. Table 4.3 also reveals that Banks' credit to private sector negatively ($B = -2.7774$) and significantly ($p = 0.0091$) predicts economic growth in Nigeria. This indicates that every billion naira increase in the value of banks' credit to private sector can be used to significantly predict a decline in economic growth by 2.8 billion naira. On the other hand, the OLS results revealed that banks' total assets positively ($B = 3.5794$) and significantly ($p = 0.000$) predicts economic growth in Nigeria. This indicates that every billion naira increase in the value of banks' assets can be used to significantly predict an increase in economic growth by 3.5 billion naira.

The F-statistic is 186.71 and the probability value of 0.000 reveals that the overall relationship between economic growth and banking sector performance in Nigeria is significant. The R-squared value of 0.9476 further reveals that about 94% of the trend behaviour of Nigerian economic growth can be explained by the combined variations of banks' deposits, banks' credit to private sector and banks' total assets.

Granger Causality Test - shows the results of the Granger causality test for BDEP, BCPS and BTAS respectively.

Granger Causality Test for RGDP and BDEP

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Date: 01/18/22 Time: 13:23

Sample: 1986 2020

Lags: 1

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
BDEP does not Granger Cause RGDP	34	25.4371	2.E-05
RGDP does not Granger Cause BDEP		0.00679	0.9349

Source: *E-views 11.0 Granger Causality Test Output, 2022*

The results of the Granger Causality test reveal that with a probability value of 0.00002, BDEP Granger causes RGDP. However, with a p-value of 0.9349, RGDP does not Granger cause BDEP. This indicates a unidirectional causality flowing from BDEP to RGDP.

Granger Causality Test for RGDP and BDEP

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Date: 01/18/22 Time: 13:24

Sample: 1986 2020

Lags: 1

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
BCPS does not Granger Cause RGDP	34	25.6816	2.E-05
RGDP does not Granger Cause BCPS		6.99742	0.0127

Source: *E-views 11.0 Granger Causality Test Output, 2022*

The results of the Granger Causality test reveal that with a probability value of 0.00002, BCPS Granger causes RGDP. Similarly, with a p-value of 0.0127, RGDP also Granger causes BCPS. This indicates a bidirectional causality flowing between BCPS and RGDP.

Granger Causality Test for RGDP and BTAS

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Date: 01/18/22 Time: 12:42

Sample: 1986 2020

Lags: 1

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
BTAS does not Granger Cause RGDP	34	15.4172	0.0004
RGDP does not Granger Cause BTAS		9.73312	0.0039

Source: *E-views 11.0 Granger Causality Test Output, 2022*

The results of the Granger Causality test reveal that with a probability value of 0.0004, BTAS Granger causes RGDP. Similarly, with a p-value of 0.0039, RGDP also Granger causes BTAS. This indicates a bidirectional causality flowing between BTAS and RGDP.

Test of Hypotheses

To test the hypotheses of this study, the p-values of the Granger Causality test were employed. The decision rule is that the null hypothesis is rejected in favor of the alternate hypothesis, if the corresponding p-value is less than 0.05. However, if the corresponding p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted at the expense of the alternate hypothesis.

As shown in table above, the corresponding p-value is 0.00002 which is less than 0.05 indicating that the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate is accepted. Therefore, bank deposits have a significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

As shown in the table, the corresponding p-value is 0.00002 which is less than 0.05 indicating that the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate is accepted. Therefore, banking credit has a significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

As shown in table, the corresponding p-value is 0.0004 which is less than 0.05 indicating that the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate is accepted. Therefore, bank total assets have a significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

Discussion of the Findings

The results of the ordinary least square revealed that banks' deposit has a negative relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. This finding does not agree with the priori expectation of the study. It shows that when bank deposit increases, economic growth declines. The relationship is however insignificant. This finding confirms the finding of Mohammed (2017) who found that bank deposit did not significantly impact economic growth. Ayunku and Etale (2014) also found that deposit liabilities negatively affected real economic growth in Nigeria. Increase in the amount of deposits culminates into an increase in credit extended and a decline in interest rate on lending. Ayunku and Etale (2014) further found that such credit has had negative impact on economic growth.

The findings of the study also revealed that against apriori expectation of the study, banking sector credit negatively and significantly predicted economic growth in Nigeria. By implication, it can be predicted increase in credit to private sector would coincide with a decline in economic growth in Nigeria. The relationship between both variables was also found to be significant. This finding is similar to the findings of Ishioro (2017) who found a negative relationship between banking sector credit to the private sector and economic growth in Nigeria. Akinwale and Obagunwa (2019) also found that Credit to General Commerce (CGC) negatively influenced economic growth in Nigeria and that CGC granger caused RGDP. Likewise, in investigating the effect of financial sector development on economic growth in Nigeria, Agbo and Nwankwo (2018) found that banking sector credit to the private sector has a negative effect on economic growth in Nigeria. The result of the Granger Causality test also revealed that this relationship also stems from an effect of bank credit on economic growth. Having found a bi-directional causality between both variables, increased extension of credit to the private sector has significantly impacted the level of economic growth in Nigeria. On the other hand, improved economic growth has caused a decline in the extension of credit to the private sector. This finding reveals the sorry state of credit extension in the country. Credit to private sector usually comes at high interest rate and requires high collateral and other strict conditions (Odufuye, 2017). Under such conditions, such credit hampers economic activities and frustrates growth. However, with increase in economic growth, credit to private sector becomes less desirable. This is a far cry from the situation in other countries like Palestine, European Union countries and OECD economies where banking credit was found to positively affect economic growth (Mohammed, 2017; Prochniak and Wasiak, 2017)

Finally, the findings of the study showed that in line with the researcher's expectation, banks' total assets have a positive and significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria. This finding disproves the findings of Ishioro (2017) who found that the size of the banking sector does not enhance economic growth in Nigeria. However, the findings of the study of Prochniak and Wasiak (2017) who found that assets ratio of banks positively and significantly impact economic growth. Causality results revealed that the amount of assets acquired by the deposit money banks actually affect the level of economic growth and in turn, the level of economic growth causes a change in the asset base of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Conclusion

The banking sector significantly affects the performance of the Nigerian economy however, it has not been to desired effects. Particularly, the total assets of the banking sector have immensely contributed to the growth of the Nigerian economy and with further economic progress, the assets of the banking sector has also recorded improvement. However, the banking sector has been unable to manage bank deposit in such a way that is beneficial to the growth of the Nigerian economy. Savings and timed deposit represent the finance of the banking public set-side for futuristic purposes. Such deposits remain dormant unless it is channeled by the banks into productive outlets. The finding of the study confirms that the banks have not been able to efficiently do so. The extension of credit to the private sector has also been found to be counterproductive.

The finding of the study and conclusion prompts the researcher to make the following recommendations;

1. Banks should restructure the conditions of the credits extended to the private sector in such a way that would ensure that such loans are beneficial for productivity and not counterproductive. This could involve an easy interest rate or extended maturity.
2. Banks also restructure the model of handling deposits to ensure that they are channeled to the most beneficial and productive investment outlets.
3. Banks should ensure that the they continue to increase their real and financial asset base to ensure they are sizeable enough to continue to contribute to the economic growth of Nigeria.

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